

WORKS FOR WORKS: PAST, PRESENT + FUTURE HISTORY

GANTT CHART 2011-2025

Project/Year	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
Mobility															
VAA&A Australia, China, UK, France, Slovenia, Italy, Austria, Greece	PHD	PHD CSP BK1 EX1	PHD	PHD CSP BK2 EX2											
KSL USA, Slovenia, Italy, UK, India, China				CTM	FSP LJU CTM PBK BK1	CTF HKU USJ KMB IPW	CTF GCF BIH PBK BK2								
LL USA, Australia							OOI	OOI IPW P2P	OOI MTA						
W4W1 USA, Germany, Slovenia, UK, UAE, India									JLU AVA KSA ACA ALN TBA	MTA WLT	MTA GVM WLT GCF NON				
W4W2 USA, UK, Spain, Mexico, India, Slovenia, Italy											MTA ACR WCI CLC JGL ZRC	MTA PBK BK1 NON JGL ZRC	MTA GCF APA JSL CSL ZRC		
EO1 USA, UK, India, Slovenia, Italy, TBD													MTA AVA VAB ZRC GVM WLT	MTA WLT PBK BK2 GVM ZRC	WLT AVA MTA GVM TBD

RESEARCH PROJECTS 2011-2024

VAA&A = Visual Agency in Art & Architecture
 KSL = Knowledge, Spirit, Law
 LL = Lived Law
 W4W1 = Works for Works: Phase One
 W4W2 = Works for Works: Phase Two
 EO1 = The Edition of One

EVENTS & ALLIANCES 2011-2024

ACA = Abhivyakti City Arts Project
 ACR = Arts Club Riera
 ALN = Arts, Letters, Numbers
 APA = American Philosophical Association
 AVA = Academy of Visual Arts
 BIH = Birkbeck Institute for the Humanities
 BK1 = Book One
 BK2 = Book Two
 CLC = Critical Legal Conference
 CSL = Benjamin Cardozo School of Law
 CSP = Cambridge Scholars Publishing
 CTF = CEPT Teaching Fellowship
 CTM = Center for Transformative Media, Parsons
 EX1 = Exhibition One
 EX2 = Exhibition Two
 FSP = Fulbright Specialist Program
 GCF = Giorgio Cini Foundation
 GVM = Garli Vikas Mandal
 HKU = Hong Kong University

IPW = Intellectual Property Watch
 JGL = Jindal Global Law School
 JLU = Justus Liebig University
 JSL = International Journal for the Semiotics of Law
 KSA = Kingston School of Art
 KMB = Kochi-Muziris Biennale
 LJU = University of Ljubljana
 MTA = Metropolitan Transmedia Authority
 NON = Nonterritorial
 OOI = Out of India Collective
 PBK = Punctum Books
 PHD = Deakin University
 P2P = P2P Foundation
 TBA = Thyssen-Bornemisza Art Contemporary
 TBD = To Be Determined
 USJ = University of St. Joseph, Macau
 VAB = Venice Architecture Biennale
 WCI = World Capital Institute
 WLT = University of Westminster Law & Theory Lab
 ZRC = ZRC-SAZU